

Research Article

Nutrient-Antinutrient Components and Isolation of Probiotic Bacteria Presence in
Ackee (*Blighia sapida*) Fruit

^{1*}Lawal, R.T., ²Olakunle, T.P., ¹Oyeleke, G.O., ³Adepeju, A.B.,
¹Olagunju, E.O. and ²Alaje, D.O.

¹Osun State Polytechnic, Iree, Nigeria, Department of Science Laboratory Technology

²Osun State Polytechnic, Iree, Nigeria, Department of Applied Sciences

³Joseph Ayo Babalola University, Ikeji Arakeji, Nigeria, Department of Food Science
and Technology

*Corresponding author: lawalrtunde@gmail.com

Abstract

*This research work covers phytochemical analysis, mineral analysis, pH, bile salt and temperature components of Ackee fruit. The phytochemical properties of the Ackee fruit (arils) showed six bioactive constituents: phytate (18.12 ± 0.08 mg/g), tannin (0.93 ± 0.04 mg/g), phenol (26.19 ± 0.08 %), glycoside (106.73 ± 0.04 mg/g), alkaloid (19.70 ± 0.02 %) while glycoside was found to be highest and tannin the least abundant. The mineral contents sodium (Na) (25.34 ± 0.03 mg/g) and potassium (K) (202.01 ± 0.02 mg/g) were determined by flame photometry while other minerals content were iron (Fe) (0.51 ± 0.01 mg/g), magnesium (Mg) (21.02 ± 0.02 mg/g), and calcium (Ca) (26.00 ± 0.01 mg/g) respectively were analysed by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) and Two strains of *Lactobacillus* sp (*Lactobacillus leschmanni* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus*) were isolated from Ackee edible portion and their identification was done by biochemical and morphological tests. Results showed that all tested isolates were able to grow at low pH 3.0 at 6.5% bile concentration and 45°C.*

Keywords: *B. sapida*, Probiotic, Temperature, pH, Tolerance, Bile-salt.

Received: 28 March 2017

Accepted: 01 July 2017

Introduction

Blighia sapida commonly known as Ackee, is an inherent tree crop of West African, present in tropical and subtropical environments. The ripe arils of the Ackee fruit yellow to cream coloured, are nutty-flavoured and edible, the arils are the major component of Jamaican national dish, Ackee and salt fish (Ekue *et al.*, 2010).

Some flowering and fruit occurs all the years in Jamaica. Flowering and fruiting occurs in spring and midsummer respectively in Florida. Crops are harvested February through April and July through October in Bahamas (Kean and Hare, 1980).

Throughout history man has turned nature into various substances such as medicines, food and domestic aids, medicinal plants plays a vital role in the management of various diseases, *Blighia sapida* of the family *Sapindaceae* is one of nature gifts which have been highly utilized for various purpose by man. It belongs to sub kingdom; tracheobionta; rosidae, order; saphindales, family *Sapindaceae* and genus; *Blighia*. Its bionomical name is *Blighia sapida*, the French name are aki and arbe fricassee. Its Spanish names are arbol de seso and seso vegata. Mexico name are arbor del hvevo and pera roja, Colombia name are bien me sabe or pan guesito. In Portuguese, it is castamta or casstanheiro de African, in Nigeria, it is known ackee and ishin. It has many other dialectal names in other western African countries (Micheal, 1998).

The fruit is a leathery, pear shaped, more or less distinctly 3-lobed capsule 2.75 to 4 inch (7-10cm), basically yellow, more or less flushed with bright scarlet. When the fruit is fully mature, it split open revealing 3 cream-coloured, flashy, glossy arils attached to the large, black, nearly round, smooth hard shining seeds-normally 3 with 1 or 2 often aborted. The base of each arils is attached to the inside of the stem-end of the jacket (Morton, 1987).

The aqueous extract of the seed is administered as parasite expellant. The treatment is followed by a saline or oily purgative. The crushed new foliage is applied on the forehead as headache reliever. The leaf juice is employed as eye drops in ophthalmia and conjunctivitis. Various preparation add combination of extract have been made for the treatment of diseases such as dysentery, epilepsy, yellow fever (Kean and Hare, 1980) and diabetic (Ibolade, 2009). The plant has been reported to be effective against cold and pain when applied. It is as well acaricidal and insecticidal (Mitchell, 2001).

The extracts of the leaves are used as eye drop in ophthalmia and conjunctivitis: locally, various part of *Blighia sapida* plants are used either alone or in combination for the

treatment of psychosis, cancer, gonorrhoea, stomach ache, hernia, backache, diarrhoea and constipation (Gbolade, 2009).

Each of the antinutrient of Ackee fruit has its function; tannin is a polyphenolic compound that either bonds and precipitates or shrinks proteins and various other organic compounds including amino acids and alkaloids. The astringency from the tannins is what causes the dry and prickly feeling in the mouth following the consumption of unripped fruit or red wine, likewise the destruction or modification of tannins with time plays an important role in ripening of fruit and aging wine (Oyeleke and Odedeji, 2011). Probiotics are usually defined as microbial food supplements that when administered in adequate amounts exert beneficial effects on the host. Evidence for probiotic health promoting effects for few well-characterized LAB strains in increasing (Saarel *et al.*, 2000). Recent scientific investigation has supported a role for probiotics as a part of a healthy diet for human and animals and may be an avenue to provide a safe, cost effective, barrier against microbial infection (Parvez *et al.*, 2006).

Materials and Methods

Fruit used were obtained from Masifa-Ile, Ejigbo Local Government, Osun State western part of Nigeria. The fresh sample was sun dried for 3 days and was later oven-dried for another 2 days at 60°C which was immediately blended using laboratory blender (MeRCK) at 15000rpm and was carefully packed in air tight polythene bag and kept in a refrigerator at 4°C until further analysis.

Minerals Analysis of *Blighia sapida*

Various elements like Na, Ca, Mg, Fe and P were analysed from *Blighia sapida*. The ash of the samples were analysed for their mineral contents. The sodium (Na) and potassium (K) content determined by Flame Emission Spectrophotometer (FES) (Model Gallenamp flame Analyser) while others calcium (Ca) magnesium (Mg), iron (Fe) and phosphorus (P) were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer method (AAS) (Model 721-2000) (AOAC 1995).

Phytochemical Analysis of *Blighia sapida*

Phytate and tannin were determined using AOAC (1995) methods, oxalate content was by the titrimetric method (AOAC, 1995) while phenol by Makkar *et al.*, (1997), Alkaloid and glycoside was determined using alkaline picrate method of Onwuka and Olopade (2005).

Isolation of Lactic Acid Bacteria from Ackee (*Blighia sapida*)

Lactic acid bacteria were isolated from edible portion of *Blighia sapida*. 5g of the edible of *Blighia sapida* was carefully blended with sterile distilled water, 1 gram of the sample was transferred into screw cap bottle containing 9ml of sterile saline water and serially diluted in 3 set of the bottles, 1ml aliquot of the sample was spread plated into selective medium De-mann rogosa sharp (MRS) (Dave and Shah, 1996) and incubated at 37°C for 24hrs anaerobically for isolation. The selected colonies were purified by streak plate technique. The purified bacterial strains were stored at 80°C in sterile reconstituted skin milk 14% (w/v) supplemented with 15% glycerol.

Resistance to Low pH

Lactic acid bacteria isolate obtained from overnight culture were invested centrifugation for 10min at 5000rpm and 4°C washed twice with PBS buffer (pH 7.2) and adjusted to pH 3.0 resistances were assessed in triplicate in term of visible colony counts and on unverated on MRS agar after incubation at 37°C for 24hrs (Maragkoudasika *et al.*, 2006).

Tolerance to Bile Salt

The tolerance against bile salt was carried out based on the intestinal bile concentration. MRS medium containing 0.3% (w/v) bile concentration was incubated with overnight culture of lactic acid bacteria. Viable colonies were counted after 24hrs of incubation on MRS agar (Bassyouni *et al.*, 2012).

Results**Mineral Analysis of *Blighia sapida***

Mineral analysis was shown in Table 1, the result of the minerals analysis showed that the sample contain sodium (25.34 ± 0.03 mg/kg), potassium (202.01 ± 0.02 mg/kg), calcium (26.00 ± 0.01 mg/kg), magnesium (21.02 ± 0.02 mg/kg) and iron (0.51 ± 0.01 mg/kg).

Phytochemical Analysis of *Blighia sapida*

The antinutrient analysis result of the sample was shown in table 2, from the results, phytate (18.12 ± 0.08 mg/g), tannins (0.93 ± 0.04 mg/g), phenols (26.19 ± 0.08 %), glycoside (106.73 ± 0.04 mg/g) and alkaloids (19.70 ± 0.02 %).

pH, Bile Salt and Temperature

It indicate the present of pH in both isolates at the range of (3.0) and bile salt 6.5% are both present, then the suitable temperature for both isolates was 45°C.

Table 1. Mineral Analysis of *Blighia sapida*

PARAMETER	RESULT ± S.D mg/kg
Sodium (Na)	25.34±0.03
Potassium (K)	202.01±0.02
Calcium (Ca)	26.00±0.01
Magnesium (Mg)	21.02±0.02
Iron (Fe)	0.51±0.01

Table 2. Phytochemical Analysis of *Blighia sapida*

PARAMETER	RESULT ± S.D
Phytate (mg/g)	18.12±0.08
Tannin (mg/g)	0.93±0.04
Phenol (%)	26.19±0.08
Glycoside (mg/g)	106.73±0.04
Alkaloid (%)	19.70±0.02

Table 3. pH, Bile Salt and Temperature

CHARACTERISTICS	A	B
pH (3.0)	+	+
Bile Salt (6.5%)	+	+
Temperature (45°C)	+	+

Key:

+ = Good growth

- = Very weak growth

A = *Lactobacillus leschmanni*

B = *Lactobacillus acidophilus*

Discussion

The mineral analysis of edible portion of *Blighia sapida* fruit as shown in Table 1. The least abundant minerals were Fe (0.51±0.01mg/kg), Mg (21.02±0.02mg/g), Na (25.34±0.03mg/g) and Ca (26.00±0.01mg/kg) while K was found to be the most abundant mineral (202.01± 0.02mg/kg). The result is in line with the observation of Olaofe and Sanni (1998) that reported K to be the most predominant mineral in Nigeria Agricultural products. It is recommended by Lawal *et al.*, (2015) that when Na\K ratio is less than one, it indicates that consumption of fruit would probably reduce high blood pressure disease.

52

The magnesium content of Ackee fruit ($21.02 \pm 0.02 \text{mg/kg}$) was lower than that of Ackee pulp and pulp oil of (21.12mg/kg) reported by Ferrao *et al.*, (1987). Mineral content acts as an activator of many enzymes system and maintains the electrical potential in nervous system (Ferrao *et al.*, 1987).

Calcium value of Ackee fruit ($26.00 \pm 0.01 \text{mg/kg}$) in this analysis is lower when compared with African star apple of 78.00mg/kg reported by Lawal *et al.*, (2016). Calcium plays an important role in blood clotting metabolic processes.

The sodium content was found to be ($25.34 \pm 0.03 \text{mg/kg}$) unit for Ackee fruit which is lower than 0.69mg/kg (unit) obtained for star apple by Lawal *et al.*, (2016). Iron has the lowest value in the result of minerals analysis for Ackee fruit (use either Ackee fruit or *Blighia sapida*).

The results of the phytochemical properties were presented in Table 2. The tannins content in Ackee fruit (0.93mg/g) was lower compared to the value 0.121mg/g reported for pawpaw fruit (Oyeleke and Odedeji, 2011). It was noticed that tannins is much more in the seed of Ackee than in the arils. Tannin is a polyphenolic compound that either binds or precipitates or shrunk proteins and various other organic compounds including amino acids and alkaloids.

Glycosides and phenols has the lowest value in Ackee fruit ($106.73 \pm 0.04 \text{mg/g}$ and $26.19 \pm 0.08\%$) compared to that of the ripe seed and unripe seed of Ackee ($109.25 \pm 0.81 \text{mg/g}$ and $202.25 \pm 0.83\%$) (Jahon, 1998). The value of alkaloids content in Ackee fruit is found to be ($19.70 \pm 0.02\%$) which is higher than $0.35 \pm 0.01\%$ and $0.48 \pm 0.02\%$ reported for ripe and unripe seed of Ackee (Madziga *et al.*, 2010). It was noticed that higher concentration of alkaloids are used in pharmaceuticals as narcotics, analgesics, antispasmodic and antibacterial agent, as anesthetics and central nervous systems (CNS) stimulants (Madziga *et al.*, 2010). Phytate value of 18.2mg/g is considered higher in Ackee fruit than 0.928mg/g of pulp and pulp oil of Ackee as reported by Aremu *et al.* (2006).

A total of two producing bacteria strains isolated from Ackee fruit were considered at presumption LAB because they were gram positive, catalase negative, motility negative and long rod cell. The growth of the *Lactobacillus* species from Ackee fruit were identified at pH 3.0 and species 45°C . Following the method highlighted lactic acid bacteria identification by Kozaki *et al.* (1992), the isolates were identified as *Lactoballius acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus laschmanni*. These strains fermented cellobiose, lactose, sucrose significantly, little fermentation occurred in mellibiose and mannitol while no fermentation was observed with raffinose and gluconate. From industrially useful lactic

acid bacteria point of view is the ability to grow at high temperature with a desirable trait as it could translate to increase rate of growth and lactic acid production.

Being resistant to low pH is one of the major selection criteria for probiotic strain to reach the small intestine and pass through stressful condition of the stomach (Cakir *et al.*, 2003). Although in the stomach, pH can be low as 1.0 but in most invitro assay, pH 3.0 has been preferred. Due to the fact that a significant decrease in the probability of strain is often observed at pH 2.0 and below (Prasad *et al.*, 1998) for buffer solution, therefore, the pH is always adjusted to 3.0. Since the taken during the digestion in the stomach is 3hours, all the isolate were examined to determine whether they were resistant to pH 3.0 within 3hours or not. All the tested isolate were able to survive at pH 3.0 during the incubation. *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Lactobacillus leschmanni* were more resistance to low pH than other strain and this correlate with the previous report by Argyri *et al.* (2013).

Resistance to bile salt is generally considered as essential properties for probiotic strains to survive the conditions in the same intestine. The presence of bile salts in the environment of bacteria culture is much more detrimental than the effect of low pH. The choice of bile concentration selected for the screening (6.5%) was based on the assumption that it's physiological concentration in the human bile (Hofmann, 1991, Brashears *et al.*, 2003). Many authors investigated the effect of bile salt concentration in the range of 0-0.4% on the *Lactobacillus* lactic survival and they reported inhibiting effect of bile salt at concentration over 0.04%. Olejnik *et al.*, (2005) reported that all bacterial cells were killed at 0.2% and above.

The results of our experiments showed much more resistance to detrimental actions of bile salts where the viability of strains of *Lactobacillus leschmanni* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus* seemed to improve when exposed to high levels of oxgall (0.4%). Few of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* strains showed significant acid bile tolerance. This observation was contrary to the findings of Liong and Shah (2005), where most strains of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* showed greater acid tolerance.

Conclusion

The isolation and derivatization of toxic hypoglycins from Ackee plant open ways for researchers to explore the interesting biological molecules found in it to enhance its probable use as drug (glucose inhibitor in diabetes). The indiscriminate consumption of Ackee fruit however should stop because it has very high anti-nutrient values that could be toxic to the body.

References

- AOAC (1995). Official Method of Analysis of AOAC International. 16th Edition. Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington DC. 56-87.
- Aremu, M.O., Olaofe, O. And Akintayo, T.E. (2006). A Comparative Study on the Chemical and Amino Acid Composition of Some Nigerian Underutilized Legume Flours. *Pak. J. Nutr* 5: 34-38.
- Argyri, A.A., Zoumpopouion, G., Karatza, K.A., Tsakalidou, E., Nychas, G.J., Panagou, F.Z. and Tassou, C.C. (2013). Selection of Potential Probiotic Lactic Acid Bacteria from Fermented Olives by Invitro Test. *Food Microbial.* 33: 282-291.
- Ashurst, P.R. (1971). Toxic Substance of Ackee. *Review J. Sci. Reso. Council Jamaica*, 2: 4-16.
- Bassyouni, R.H., Abdel-All, W.S., Fadi, M.G., Abdel-All. S. and Kamel, Z. (2012). Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from Dairy Product in Egypt as Probiotic. *Life Sci. J.* 9: 2924-2930.
- Begley M., Gahan. C.G. and Hill, C. (2005). The Interaction between Bacteria and Bile. *FFMS Microbiol.*, 72: 1729-1738.
- Breashears, M.M., Jaron, D. and Trimble, J. (2003). Isolation. Selection and Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria for a Competitive Exclusion Product to Reduce Shedding of *Escherichia coli* 0157: F17 in cattle. *J. Food Prot.* 66: 355-363.
- Cakir, I. (2003). Determination of Some Probiotic Properties on *Lactobacilli* and *Bifidobacteria*. Ankara University Thesis of Ph.D. 49-62.
- Dave, R.I. and Shah, N.P. (1996). Evaluation of Media for Selective Enumeration of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* & *Bifidobacterium* sp. *J. Dairy Sci.* 79: 1529-1536.
- Ekue, M.R.M., Sinsin, B., Eyog-Matig, O. and Finkeldey.R. (2010). Uses Traditional Management, Perception of Variation and Preferences in Ackee (*Blighia sapida* K.D. Koenig) Fruit Traits in Benin: Implication for Domestication and Conservation. *J. Ethnobiol. & Ethnomed*, 6(12): 1-14.

Ferrao, J.E.M., Ferro, A.M.B.C. and Autures, A.M.G. (1987). Bambara Groundnut (*Vigna subterranean*) Aspect of its Nutritive Value *Gracia de orta seriod Estudos Agronomics*. 14: 35-39.

Gbolade, A.A. (2009). Inventory of Antidiabetic Plants in Selected Districts of Lagos State, Nigeria. *J. Ethnopharmacol.* 121: 135-139.

Hofmann, A. (1991). Enterohepatic Circulation of Bile Salt. In: Schultz (eds). *Handbook of Physiology*, Section 6: the Gastrointestinal System. 567-580.

Jahon, W.J.N. and Brown, D.E. (1998). *Chemical from Plants, Perspectives Pon Plant Secondary Product*, Imperial College Press, London UK. 2-5.

Kean, E.A. and Haro, E.R. (1980). Gamma Glutamyl Trans Strain Peptidase of the Ackee Plant *Blighia sapida* Phytochemical. *Inter. J. Microbiol.*, 12: 4-19.

Kozaki, M., Uchimura, T. and Sanae, O. (1992). *Laboratory Manual for Identification of Lactic Acid Bacteria*. Tokyo, Japan: Asakura Bookshop. 22-29.

Lawal, R. T., Sulaiman, W. K., Ishola, A. D., Olayiwola, A. T. and Ajao, F.D. (2015). Changes in Selected Chemical Compositions of Fermented Sorghum and Maize Flours. *Asian J. Basic & Appl. Sci.* 2: (2) 50-54.

Lawal, R.T., Ishola, A.D., Sulaiman, W.K., Ajao, F.D. and Adetuberu, I.A. (2016). Some Aspects of Physiochemical Properties and Evaluation of Probiotic Isolated from African Star Apple (*Chrysophyllum albidum*). *Inter. J. Multi. Acad. Res.* 4: (2) 1-6.

Liong, M.T. and Shah, N.P. (2005). Effects of *Lactobacillus casei* Symbiotic on Serum Lipoprotein Intestinal Microflora and Organic Acid in Rats. *J. Dairy Sci.* 89: 1390-1399.

Madziga, S., Sanni, and Sandabe, U.K. (2010). Phytochemical and Elemental Analysis of Aealy Phawil-keslanal leaf. *Journal of American Science*. 6(1 1): 5 10-514.

Makkar, H. P. S., Becker, K., Sporer, F. and Wink, M. (1997). Studies on Nutritive Potential and Toxic Constituents of Different Provenances of *Jatropha carcus*. *J. Agric Food Chem.*, 45 : 3152-3157.

Maragkoudakisa, P.A., Zoumpopoulava, G., Miarisa, C., Kalantzopoviosa. G. Potb. B. and Tsakalidou, E. (2006). Probiotic Potential of *Lactobacillus* Strains Isolated from Dairy Products. *Int. Dairy J.*, 16: 189-199.

Michael, T.G., Williams, L.A.D., Felcher, K, Singh, P.D.A., Wharfe, G. Chookang, E. Sawh, R.N. and Rickards, E. (1998). Extracts from *Blighia sapida* (Koenig) Produce Neutropenia and Thrombocytopenia in Mice. *Phytotherapy Research*, 10(8): 689-691.

Mitchell, S.A. and Ahmad, M.H. (2001). A New Review of Medicinal Plant Research at the University of the West Indies, *Jamaica*. 254.

Morton, J.F. (1987). Ackee, In: Fruits of Warm Climates. 269-271.

Odebiyi, O.O. and Sofowora, E.A. (1979). Phytochemical Screening of Nigeria Medicinal Plant (2nd OAU/STRC).

Olaofe, O. and Sanni, C.O. (1988). Mineral Contents of Agriculture Product Food Chem. 30: 73- 79.

Olejnik, A., Lewandowska, M., Obarska, M. and Grajek, W. (2005). Tolerance of *Lactobacillus* and *Bfidobacterium sp.* Strains to Low pH, Bile Salts and Digestive Enzymes. *Electr. J. Polish Agric. Univer., Food Sci. & Technol.* 8 (1) : 1171 - 1185.

Ong, A.S.H., Choo, Y.M. and Ool, C.K. (1995). In Developments in Oils and Fats. R.J. Hamilton, edtn, pp. 153-191. Blackie Academic and Professional Glasgow winter African Symposium on Traditional Pharmacopodia and African Medicine. 216-220.

Onwuka, S.K. and Olopade, J. O (2005). Some Aspects of the Clinical Anatomy of the Mandibular and Maxillofacial Regions of the West African Dwarf Goat in Nigeria. *Int. J. Morphol.*, 23(1): 33-36.

Oyeleke, W.A. and Odedeji, J.O. (2011). Effect of Different Waxing Material on Some Chemical Properties, Minerals and Antinutrients Compositions of Pawpaw (*Carica papaya*). *Pak. J. Nutr.*, 10 (11): 1008-1012.

Parvez, S., Malik, K.A., Kang, S.A., Kim, H.Y. (2006). Probiotics and their Fermented Food Products are Beneficial for Health. *J. Appl. Microbial.* 100: 1171 - 1185.

Prasad, J., Gill, H., Smart, J. and Gopal, P.K. (1998). Selection and Characterization of *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium* Strains for use as Probiotics. *Int. Dairy J.* 8(12): 993- 1002.

Saarela, M., Mogenson, G., Fonden, R., Maho, J. and Mahila-Sandholm, T. (2000). Probiotic Bacteria, Safety, Functional and Technological Properties. *J. Biotechnol.* 84: 197-215.